

ON THE PREPARATION OF *o*- AND *p*-NITRO PROPIOPHENONES

BY AMITABHA RAY CHAUDHURI AND T. N. GHOSH

Starting from phenylethyl carbinol, *o*- and *p*-nitropropiophenones have been prepared.

In connection with synthesis of certain derivatives of nitrophenylpropane, the characteristic chain, as present in chloromycetin, *o*- and *p*-nitropropiophenones became necessary and were prepared by a process that is described in the body of the paper.

Commanducci and Pescitelli (*Gazzetta*, 1906, 36, 787) claimed to have obtained *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitropropiophenones by the action of fuming nitric acid on propiophenone under different conditions. But the characteristics of *o*- and *p*-isomers, as recorded by these authors, could not be confirmed by subsequent workers (Wohnlich, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1913, 251, 529; Auwers and Duesberg, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 1179; Hartung *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 4149). The nitration of propiophenone, however, has been found to yield a mixture of *m*- and *o*-nitropropiophenones. The most favourable conditions for nitration, in order to get these two isomers, have been described by Zenitz and Hartung (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1946, 11, 444). Hartung and Foster (*J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc., Sci. Ed.*, 1946, 35, 15) have subsequently prepared *p*-nitropropiophenone in about 25% yield from *p*-aminopropiophenone via the diazonium borofluoride, the replacement of the diazonium group by the nitro group having been effected according to the method of Starkey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1479). As this method of Hartung and Foster appeared rather tedious, an alternative method of preparation of *p*-nitropropiophenone has now been sought. Ford-Moore and Rydon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 679) have obtained *o*- and *p*-nitroacetophenones in almost equal amounts by nitrating phenylmethyl carbinol in presence of acetic anhydride, hydrolysing the mixed nitro-acetates and separating the *o*- and *p*-nitrophenylmethyl carbinols. The latter compounds have been then oxidised with chromic acid to the corresponding nitroacetophenones.

Following the above method of Ford-Moore and Rydon, the nitration of phenylethyl carbinol in acetic anhydride has now been studied and has been found to yield, through the stages of hydrolysis, separation of the isomers by fractional distillation and subsequent oxidation with chromic acid, *o*- and *p*-nitropropiophenones in overall yields of 26% and 16.7% respectively. These ketones have been characterised by the formation of oxime and semicarbazone, and oxidation to the corresponding nitrobenzoic acids with alkaline permanganate.

EXPERIMENTAL

(All the nitrogen analyses recorded below have been carried out according to Kjeldahl method, the Dumas method having been not found feasible due to sudden decomposition of the compounds concerned).

Nitration of Phenylethyl Carbinol.—Phenylethyl carbinol (1.36 g.) was added dropwise to a cooled mixture of acetic anhydride (200 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (1 c.c.).

After being kept at room temperature (30°) for about 45 minutes, the acetic anhydride solution of phenylethylcarbinyl acetate was stirred, while fuming nitric acid (48 c.c., *d* 1.5) was added dropwise over 2 hours, the temperature being maintained at 15°-18°. After being stirred for a further period of 2 hours at 15°-18°, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-water. Next day the heavy oil (mixture of nitrophenylpropyl acetates) was separated, thoroughly washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and was subsequently hydrolysed by refluxing for 6 hours with alcohol (500 c.c., 95%) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.). The residue, obtained by evaporation on a water-bath under reduced pressure, was then fractionated, using an efficient fractionating column. Three fractions were collected: the first (62 g.), b.p. 140°-145°/0.1 mm.; the middle (20 g.), b.p. 145°-155°/0.1 mm.; and the end one (46 g.), b.p. 155°-165°/0.1 mm.

When redistilled, the first fraction had b.p. 142°-144°/0.1 mm. (Found: N, 7.47. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 7.73 per cent) and the end one had b.p. 161°-162°/0.1 mm. (Found: N, 7.38. $C_9H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 7.73 per cent). These two fractions have been found by oxidation (*vide infra*) to be *o*- and *p*-nitrophenylethyl carbinols respectively. The middle fraction has been found to be a mixture of these two isomers.

The first fraction has furnished, with acetic anhydride and a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid, α -(*o*-nitrophenyl) propyl acetate as a pale yellow liquid, b.p. 158°-160°/6-7 mm (Found: N, 5.92. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 6.28 per cent).

The end fraction has likewise furnished α -(*p*-nitrophenyl) propyl acetate crystallising from aqueous alcohol in colorless, rectangular plates, m.p. 58°. (Found: N, 5.89. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 6.28 per cent).

Oxidation of the above First and End Fractions: (a) Preparation of o-Nitropropio-phenone.—The first fraction (60 g.) was added dropwise under stirring to a mixture of sodium dichromate (98 g.), water (250 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) and the resulting mixture, maintained at 55°-60°, was stirred for three and half hours, and then poured into ice-water. The product was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was washed with 10% aqueous sodium carbonate solution and dried. After removal of the ether, the residue was distilled and *o*-nitropropio-phenone (average yield 46.5 g.) was collected at 155°-158°/6-7 mm. (Zenitz and Hartung, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 152°-155°/2-3 mm.). (Found: N, 7.61. $C_9H_9O_3N$ requires N, 7.82 per cent). Oxidation with alkaline permanganate has yielded *o*-nitrobenzoic acid (mixed m.p. 146-47°).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from aqueous alcohol in cream-coloured rectangular plates, m.p. 180-81° (Auwers and Duesberg, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 182-83°; Zenitz and Hartung, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 183-84°). (Found: N, 23.94. $C_{10}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 23.73 per cent).

(b) Preparation of p-Nitropropio-phenones.—The end fraction (44 g.) was oxidised with chromic acid in the same manner as described above. The solid residue (average yield 30 g.), left after removing the solvent, was crystallised from aqueous alcohol in pale yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 88-89° (Hartung and Foster, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 90-91°). (Found: N, 7.86. $C_9H_9O_3N$ requires N, 7.82 per cent). Oxidation with alkaline permanganate has yielded *p*-nitrobenzoic acid (mixed m.p. 239-40°).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from aqueous alcohol in cream coloured rectangular plates, m.p. 198-200° (Found: N, 24.11. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3N_4$ requires N, 23.73 per cent). The *oxime* was prepared in pyridine and was twice crystallised from aqueous alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 147-48° (Hartung and Foster, *loc. cit.*, record m.p. 124° decomp.). (Found: N; 14.12. $C_9H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 14.43 per cent).

The authors thank Dr. U. P. Basu for his interest in this investigation.

BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
CALCUTTA-16.

Received June 19, 1951.